

Effect of TETFund Sponsored Academic Staff Training and Development on the Quality of Teaching and Student Academic Performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: The study examined the effect of TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development on the teaching quality and student academic performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, (A.I.F.U.E) Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Adopting a survey design, the study investigated whether TETFund sponsored academic staff training and development significantly affects teaching quality and student academic performance in A.I.F.U.E, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Primary data were obtained from a 20- item questionnaire administered to 260 academic staff. Using descriptive statistics and the Pearson correlation, two research questions and two hypotheses were analysed. Findings showed that the two hypotheses had a correlation coefficient of 0.76 and 0.56, respectively, indicating a positive and significant relationship between TETFund-sponsorship of academic staff training and development and quality of teaching, as well as TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development and student academic performance. To ensure the sustainability of the gains of TETFund sponsorship, the study recommended the need for a university policy on regular and continuous academic staff training and development that is all inclusive. This can only be achieved through structured annual staff training and development plans in partnership with TETFund and any other willing corporate sponsor in order to reduce financial constraints on academic staff. The study also recommended that the University should have a strategic plan that will ensure fair conference participation among academic staff. This will further promote professional development among academic staff.

KEYWORDS: Training, Development, Teaching Quality, Student Academic Performance, TETFund, A.I.F.U.E, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of higher education in Nigeria, the quality of teaching and academic performance of students remain pressing issues for tertiary institutions striving to fulfil their mandates of knowledge production, human capital development, and societal transformation. At the heart of these institutional outcomes is the capacity, motivation, and effectiveness of academic staff. Investment in the training and development of academic staff is widely recognised as a critical pathway to enhancing teaching practices, improving learning experiences, and ultimately boosting students' academic performance (Ogunode, Ukozor & Chijioko, 2024). Recent research findings underscore the fact that where universities implement structured professional development for lecturers, the effectiveness of pedagogical delivery and research output improves significantly (Osunyikanmi, 2024).

Academic staff development is crucial to enhancing the quality of teaching and research in tertiary educational institutions. According to Idakwoji and Makwolo (2022), academic staff development refers to the process of improving the capacity of teachers to effectively and efficiently achieve their educational objectives. Development programs for academic staff include educational programs spanning from master's degrees to PhD and postdoctoral programs. Others include conferences, workshops, seminars, orientation, and training activities. Given the crucial role of academic staff development in tertiary educational institutions, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) was established in 2011 to sponsor human capital development, amongst other objectives. The Academic Staff Training and Development Report of TETFund for 2021 shows that, in public tertiary educational institutions in the South East, TETFund sponsored 437 scholars, locally and internationally, between January 1, 2020, and December 31, 2021, with a total sum of N5,556,702,993.90 (US\$13.39 million) (TETFund, 2021; CBN, 2021). This expenditure is comparable to the annual capital budget of public universities, highlighting the substantial amount invested in academic staff training and development. Such huge investments in human capital happen because training academics is linked to improving teacher capacity. The professional development of teachers is crucial for improving teaching strategies, increasing teacher confidence, and enhancing student engagement. (Uzorika, Kalabuki, & Odebityi, 2024). Improving teaching quality remains critical to tertiary education in Nigeria.

Quality of teaching refers to the extent to which teachers utilise strong subject expertise, with sound pedagogical strategies, to assess

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and collectively sustain student learning (Masadeh & Al-Momani, 2022; Cotta, et. al. 2024). The quality of teaching is crucial to the goals of higher education. Training of academics is expected to not only improve subject competence but also instructional delivery, student engagement, assessment, and feedback. The quality of teaching can dictate the whole essence of the instructional process. Effective instructional practices for academics can be achieved through continuous training and development. Improved learning outcomes are central to higher education goals.

Student performance is very critical in higher education. Student performance refers to outcomes that result from learning activities. Such outcomes range from knowledge, skills, and competencies to high grades and academic achievements, and ultimately to a progressive career (York, Gibson, & Rankin, 2015). Though considered broad, student performance can be narrowed down to academic achievement, such as completion of tests, assignments, course grades, and grade point averages. Meeting the goal of academic excellence requires effective teaching, monitoring, and assessment by academic staff. Training and development improve teacher capacity to contribute directly to the educational outcomes of students in higher educational institutions.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Academic staff training and development remains a challenge in Nigerian public tertiary educational institutions. With the federal annual budget for education below 10 percent, Nigerian public tertiary institutions have depended on the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) for both human capital development and infrastructural development. To bridge the existing gaps in funding of academic staff for training and development in public universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education in Nigeria, significant resources have been allocated for funding educational programs locally and internationally. Investments in conferences, scholarships, and professional development have led to an increase in the knowledge, skills, and competencies of academic staff at public higher institutions. However, the question remains whether TETFund interventions in the academic staff of public tertiary institutions have improved the quality of teaching and student academic performance. Teachers in higher institutions play the primary role of instructional delivery. The academic performance of students is also dependent on the quality of teachers. With global advancements in education, technology, and research, academic staff training and development remain crucial for equipping teachers to meet the delicate nature of their responsibilities. Innovative and creative methodologies must be pursued to produce workers needed for the current marketplace.

The claim that improving teaching capacity increases learning outcomes has not been well supported by systematic research (Zhang, Admiraal, Saab, & Liu, 2022). Empirical evidence suggests that while TETFund investments in academic staff of public tertiary institutions improve teaching quality and student performance in some institutions, challenges such as delayed funding and inequitable allocation affect the effectiveness of the sponsorship (Umar & Gimba, 2023). This study, therefore, intends to ascertain the effect of TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development on both the quality of teaching and student academic performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

1. Ascertain the effect of TETFund-sponsored training and development on quality of teaching in A.I.F.U.E, Owerri.
2. Determine the influence of TETFund-sponsored training and development on student academic performance in A.I.F.U.E, Owerri.

1.3 Research Question

1. What is the effect of TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development on quality of teaching in A.I.F.U.E, Owerri.
2. What is the effect of TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development on student academic performance in A.I.F.U.E, Owerri.

1.4 Hypotheses

- H0₁: Academic staff training and development has no significant influence on the quality of teaching at A.I.F.U.E, Owerri.
- H0₂: Academic staff training and development has no significant influence on students' academic performance at A.I.F.U.E, Owerri.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

2.1 Academic Staff Training and Development.

Staff training and development refers to the process of improving the capacity of teachers to be efficient and effective in achieving the objectives of the school system (Idakwoji C Makolo, 2022). This is achieved through the provision of opportunities for teachers to enhance their knowledge, skills, and performance in line with the goals of the institution (Mela, Modibbo, C Paul, 2024). Academic staff training and development refers to structured initiatives taken by tertiary institutions to enhance the professional knowledge, pedagogical skills, research capacity, and technological competence of academic staff (Ogunode, Ukozor C Chijioke, 2024). Staff development involves both cognitive and affective growth. Cognitive development refers to improvement in pedagogical ideas and instructional skills, while

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affective development refers to enhanced commitment and dedication to the teaching profession (Mwila, Namuchana, C Lafunguloet, 2022).

Staff development aims to build human capital, improve job performance, and thereby elevate institutional outcomes (Osunyikanmi, 2024). Training and development programs not only enable institutions to achieve their goals, but also improve the standard of the organisations (Chaudhary & Bhaskar, 2016). Educational institutions are ranked based on the capacity and competence of the human capital in general, and academic staff in particular. The scope of academic staff training often includes in-service workshops, mentoring programs, seminars, ICT training, peer review, and orientation for new lecturers. Staff development aims to build human capital, improve job performance, and thereby elevate institutional outcomes (Osunyikanmi, 2024). According to Hervie and Winful (2018), academic staff training and development consequently lead to improvement in students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The training and development of teachers remain crucial to achieving the goals of tertiary education.

2.12 Teaching Quality

Teaching quality refers to the effectiveness of academic staff in planning, delivering, assessing, and reflecting on student learning. It encompasses the use of modern pedagogical strategies, student-centered learning, effective feedback, the integration of technology, classroom engagement, and curriculum alignment (Shittu, 2024). Established research shows that teaching quality is a strong predictor of students' academic performance. Teaching quality depends not only on the teacher but on other elements beside the teacher. Classroom management, supportive climate, and cognitive activation affect teaching quality (Klieme, Pauli, & Reusser, 2009). "Good teaching is when it is done well. When teaching leads to learning, we refer to it as successful teaching. When teaching is both successful and good, it can be referred to as quality teaching" (Fenstermacher & Richardson, 2025). Quality teaching, therefore, not only enables the student to learn and pass tests but also leads to further success.

2.13. Student Academic Performance

The concept of academic performance is multifaceted, with different definitions depending on the context, which may be based on achievement, skill, career, ability, knowledge, or persistence (Kumar, Agarwal, & Agarwal, 2021). Academic performance remains a subject of interest to students, educational institutions, and society. It is a key indicator of institutional effectiveness and student learning outcomes (John, Gyang & Ndupuechi, 2024). While interaction with teachers remains one of the key determinants of students' academic performance, academic performance is the nucleus on which significant components of the tertiary education system revolve (Kumar, Agarwal, Agarwal, 2021). They further posit that better academic performance sets the prospect for the growth of nations. While student academic performance typically encompasses metrics such as grade point average (GPA), pass rate, progression, graduation, and achievement in assessments, achieving uniformity on the key metric of measurement remains difficult (Ampofo & Osei-Awusu, 2015). For this study, student academic performance refers to the degree to which a student can complete studies and related tasks (Sharma, 2012).

2.2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

The primary theoretical underpinning is the Human Capital Theory (HCT), by Becker (1964). This theory suggests that investment in human capital through education, training, and development enhances productivity and output. In a tertiary education context, training academic staff is an investment in human capital that enhances skills, knowledge, and competencies. Empirical work in Nigeria supports that staff training is positively linked to academic staff job performance (Ogunode, Ukozor & Chijioke, 2024).

2.2.2 Transformative Learning Theory

Another relevant theoretical lens is Transformative Learning Theory. The theory, postulated by Mezirow (1991), emphasizes how adult learners (such as academic staff) reflect on their assumptions and experience a change in perspective. Through professional development, academic staff can transform their teaching approaches, adopt student-centred pedagogy, integrate technology, and engage in reflective practice, thus improving teaching quality and student outcomes.

2.2.3 Human Capital Development Theory

Human Capital Development Theory, postulated by Schultz (1961), posits that education and training constitute essential investments in individuals that yield improved productivity and performance outcomes. The modern evolution of this theory emphasizes life-long learning, digital literacy, and knowledge-based competencies as central to staff effectiveness in higher education. Continuous professional development equips educators with advanced pedagogical skills, technological competence, and research capacity, all of which enhance instructional quality (OECD, 2018). Similarly, the World Bank (2021) emphasizes that higher educational institutions that prioritize systematic training programs experience improved teaching outcomes and student academic success.

2.2.4 Social Learning Theory (Digital Contextualization)

According to Bandura (1977), social learning theory asserts that learning occurs through observation, imitation, and modeling within

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social and interactive contexts. The modern digital interpretation, advanced by Siemens (2017), integrates connectivism, a learning process mediated by online collaboration, peer engagement, and knowledge sharing through digital platforms. Within academic institutions, professional learning communities, workshops, and mentorship programs enable lecturers to acquire and exchange best practices. Such collaborative networks significantly enhance instructional innovation and teacher motivation, resulting in higher student engagement and performance (Gong, Lin, & Zhang, 2020). Therefore, modern staff training programs that emphasize social interaction, teamwork, and reflective practice effectively translate into improved teaching quality.

2.3 Empirical Review

Empirical studies conducted in Nigeria and beyond have established a strong link between academic staff training and development, teaching quality, and student academic performance. However, the scope, depth, and institutional contexts of these studies vary considerably, which provides a basis for the present investigation in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

Idakwoji and Makolo (2022) conducted a descriptive survey in the North-Central zone, Nigeria, to assess the impact of in-service training, mentoring, and orientation programs on the job performance of academic staff in 15 colleges of education. Using a sample of 586 respondents, data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. The study revealed a significant positive relationship between participation in in-service training, orientation, mentoring, conferences, and subject matter delivery.

John, Gyang, and Ndupuechi (2024) investigated the relationship between staff development and compensation practices in the National Teachers Institute (NTI), North-Central Nigeria. Employing a correlational design, the study drew data from 300 staff members and 500 students. Using multiple regression analysis, the researchers found that staff professional development significantly predicted students' academic performance ($\beta = 0.741, p = 0.000$).

In another recent work, Osunyikanmi (2024) examined the effect of training and development on staff productivity within the Nigerian university system. The study adopted a mixed-methods approach involving 250 academic staff and 20 administrators across three public universities in the South-West. Findings showed that while staff development programs were often designed in line with national quality assurance frameworks, the implementation was inconsistent due to financial constraints and weak institutional support systems. The study revealed that participation alone does not guarantee improved productivity unless training content is aligned with institutional goals and follow-up mechanisms are in place.

In the South-East, Kani and Ezeodo (2023) explored the influence of professional development programs on secondary school teachers in Enugu State. Using a quasi-experimental design, the study revealed that teachers who participated in workshops and seminars demonstrated better classroom management and improved instructional delivery. This led to measurable gains in student performance in English and Mathematics. The study concluded that targeted professional development initiatives foster both teaching competence and student success. Shittu (2024) examined the nexus between teacher quality and student performance in Osun State, with in-service training as the human capital development. Utilizing a longitudinal dataset spanning three academic years, the study found that teacher exposure to training significantly predicted students' test scores in core subjects ($F = 8.96, p < 0.01$). The study emphasized that teachers who regularly participated in pedagogical and ICT workshops demonstrated enhanced teaching strategies and classroom engagement. Uzorka, Kalabuki, & Odebiyi (2024) examined the effectiveness of in-service teacher training programs in enhancing teaching quality and student achievement in Kampala. Data for the study were obtained from 286 in-service teachers from schools around Kampala. In addition, 52 in-service teachers were interviewed. Analysis was carried out with chi-square and regression analyses. Findings revealed that in-service training and professional development affected teacher quality and improved student performance.

Hussaini, Uba, and Sifawa (2023) assessed the relationship between staff development programs and teacher performance in Sokoto State. Using a stratified random sampling of 150 academic staff, their descriptive and inferential analyses (t-test and ANOVA) revealed a significant relationship between participation in development programmes and improved teacher performance ($p < 0.05$).

Collectively, these empirical findings affirm that academic staff training and development are pivotal determinants of teaching quality and student performance. However, notable gaps persist. Firstly, the majority of studies are confined to secondary education or non-university contexts. Secondly, many employed descriptive designs without longitudinal or experimental approaches capable of establishing causal relationships. Consequently, the present study seeks to fill these gaps by empirically investigating the impact of academic staff training and development on both teaching quality and students' academic performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research survey design, suitable for the collection and analysis of primary data. Respondents consisted of academic staff of Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State. A total of 260 academic staff from six faculties, twenty-five departments, ranging from lecturer 11 to professors, were randomly selected from the University's population of 788 academic staff to constitute the sample for the study. The study utilized a questionnaire divided into two segments. Section A

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captured the demographic characteristics of the respondents, while Section B had 20 question items on academic staff training and development (AST&D), teaching quality (TQ), and academic performance (AP). The questionnaire was administered directly to the respondents and collected immediately, which led to a high rate of return. The items in Section B were rated using a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). A reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's Alpha test to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The analysis of the items relating to research questions one and two yielded reliability coefficients of 0.978 and 0.988. This gave an average reliability value of 0.98. The results affirm the internal consistency in respondents' responses. Data were analysed with simple percentages, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), and Pearson correlation. The demographic characteristics of the respondents were examined with simple percentages. Research questions one and two were analysed with descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), where only mean values above 2.5 were considered acceptable. Pearson correlation was utilized to analyse hypotheses one and two. A p-value less than 0.05 indicated rejection of the null hypothesis, while a p-value equal to or greater than 0.05 indicated acceptance of the alternative hypothesis.

3.1 RESULTS

Table 4.1: Social Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Total Respondents	Percentage of Respondents	Total Respondents	Total Percentage		
				Mean	Max	Min
Gender Male Female	146 114 = 260	56.2% 43.8%	100%	130	146	114
Age 30 – 39 40 – 49 50 & Above	11 93 156 = 260	4.2% 35.8% 60.0%	100%	86.67	156	11
Year of service 5 – 10 years 11 – 15 years More than 15 years	22 146 93 = 260	8.5% 55.8% 35.7%	100%	86.67	146	22

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2025

The analysis of data collected on the respondents' demographic profile is presented in Table 1 above. The analyses indicate that 56.2% of the respondents were male, while 43.8% were female. The mean age of the respondents (67%) is 50.1 years. Respondents in the 40–49 age bracket accounted for 35.8%, while the lowest percentage (4.2%) was in the 30–39 age bracket. Regarding years of service at the University, 55.8% of respondents have served at the institution for 11 to 15 years. Those who have served for more than 15 years constituted 35.2%, while the lowest percentage of 8.3% were people who served in the University between 5–10 years. Regarding the highest qualification, 80% of respondents had a Ph.D, 18.1% had a Master's degree, and 11% were first degree holders.

Research Question One:

1. To what extent does TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development contribute to the quality of teaching in AIFUE Owerri?

Table 4.2: Respondents' responses on the extent to which TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development contribute to the quality of teaching

S/N	ITEM QUESTIONS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	TETFund-sponsored training and development has improved my teaching	182	68	10	10	3.66	0.550	Accept

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	preparedness.							
2	The training and development programs meet my academic development needs.	119	14	-	-	3.46	0.499	Accept
3	Professional development has improved my classroom confidence.	188	72	-	-	3.72	0.448	Accept
4	As a result of the training, I can engage in discussions, activities, and group activities with the students.	156	99	5	5	3.58	0.532	Accept
5	The training has made me incorporate digital tools in my class.	99	135	26	-	3.28	0.635	Accept
6	I encourage students to think critically and apply concepts.	125	135	-	-	3.48	0.501	Accept
7	I am accessible to students outside the scheduled class hours for academic inquiries.	125	130	-	5	3.44	0.603	Accept
8	Academic training has helped me to incorporate assessment procedures effectively.	172	83	-	5	3.62	0.593	Accept
9	Staff training has helped me incorporate innovative teaching practices.	162	88	5	5	3.57	0.633	Accept
10	Staff training and development have generally improved my curriculum delivery.	151	104	5	-	3.56	0.535	Accept
	Grand Mean & SD					3.537	0.5529	Accept

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2025

Table 4.2 above presents respondents' responses to the extent to which academic staff development affects the quality of teaching. Analysis shows that the value of the pooled mean rating is 3.537 on a 4-point Likert scale. The result shows that the extent to which academic staff development contributes to teaching quality is above expectation with the pooled mean of 3.537 higher than the expected mean of 2.5. The standard deviation grand value of 0.5529 showed that the respondents' responses are spread around the mean. The responses are consistent with one another.

Test of Hypothesis One

Table 4.3: Correlation Relationship between Academic Staff Development and Quality of Teaching

Variables	N	R (Correlation Coefficient)	r (P-value)	Remark
Quality of Teaching	260	0.686	0.00	Reject null hypothesis one

Source: SPSS 27. Where N = Number of Respondents, r = P value, R = Correlation coefficient

Table 4.3 above shows the correlation relationship between academic staff development and teaching quality. Analysis shows that the correlation probability value is 0.00, which is significant because it is less than 0.05. The results led to the rejection of null hypothesis one. The study, therefore, concluded that academic staff development significantly affects the quality of teaching. Results also show that the correlation coefficient is 0.686, which shows that the extent of the relationship between academic staff development and quality of teaching is positive and highly correlated at 68.6%.

Table 4.4 above presents respondents' responses to the extent to which TETFund- sponsored academic staff training and development influences students' academic performance. Analysis shows that the value of the pooled mean rating is 2.891 on a 4-point Likert scale. The result reveals that the extent to which TETFund- sponsored academic staff training and development

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contributes to student academic performance is above expectation, with the pooled mean of 2.891 being higher than the expected mean of 2.5. The standard deviation grand value of 0.977 shows that the respondents’ responses are spread around the mean. The responses are also consistent with one another.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H02: Academic staff training and development has no significant influence on students’ academic performance at AIFUE. Owerri.

Research Question Two:

1. What is the influence of academic staff training and development on students’ academic performance at AIFUE?

Table 4.4: Respondents’ responses on the extent to which TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development influences students’ academic performance

S/N	ITEM QUESTIONS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	The examination scores of my students improved with the training and development from TETFund.	26	136	57	41	2.57	874	Accept
2	Students perform better in class tests compared to the period before my TETFund training.	130	47	52	31	3.06	1.085	Accept
3	Student preparation for examinations has improved since my TETFund-sponsored training and development.	99	88	53	20	3.02	0.946	Accept
4	Student project scores have improved due to improved supervision skills obtained from TETFund training and development.	89	98	42	31	2.94	0.991	Accept
5	There is a consistent increase in the marks of students I teach after attending TETFund-sponsored trainings.	125	79	36	20	3.19	0.946	Accept
6	The quality of students’ projects has improved since I participated in	104	42	78	36	2.82	1.108	Accept
7	Students demonstrate better critical skills after my training.	94	47	73	46	2.73	1.132	Accept
8	The analytical and research skills of students improved after the TETFund-sponsored training.	110	68	62	20	3.03	0.986	Accept
9	Students perform better in class assignments after my TETFund-sponsored training.	84	93	52	31	2.88	0.995	Accept

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10	Student exam scores improved after the training sponsored by TETfund.	16	162	62	20	2.67	0.707	Accept
	Grand Mean/Standard Deviation					2.891	0.977	Accept

Source: Researcher’s Survey, 2025

Table 4.5 Correlation Relationship between Academic Staff Training and Development and Student Academic Performance

Variables	N	R (Correlation Coefficient)	r (P-value)	Remark
Academic Staff Training & Development	260	0.931	0.00	Reject the null hypothesis
Student Academic Performance	260			

Source: SPSS 27. Where N = Number of Respondents, r = P value, R = Correlation coefficient

Presented in Table 4.5 above is the correlation relationship between TETFund- sponsored academic staff training and student academic performance in A.I.F.U.E, Owerri, Imo State. Analysis shows that the observed correlation coefficient of 0.000 is significant ($P < 0.05$). This is because the probability value is less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance. The results, therefore, led to the rejection of the stated null hypothesis. This led to the conclusion that TETFund-sponsored academic staff training has a significant effect on student academic performance.

Data Summary of Student Academic Performance Distribution on Research

To further provide a robust analysis, extracted data on Research Project course (ED 451) from the department of English Language and Literature of the Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, between the period of March 2025 and June 2025 was analysed.

Overview of data Presentation

The analysis is based on secondary data sourced from the result sheets representing different sections of the student body within the department.

- Sheet A (37 students): Scores range from 60 to 72
- Sheet B (47 students): Scores range from 60 to 72
- Sheet C (41 students): Scores range from 60 to 72
- Sheet D (22 students): Scores ranging from 60 to 71.
- Total sample size (N): 147 students

The assessment criteria are divided into three weighted components: PROP (Proposal): Initial research design

FIN (Final): The completed research project report

SUP (Supervision/External evaluation: Practical engagement.

Table 4.6: Descriptive Statistics

Population	Highest Score	Lowest Score	Mean Score	range	Modal Grade
147	72	60	66	12 points	B

Source: Authors estimation from the results of Research Project (ED 451) in 2025. Department of English Language and Literature at Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri.

Key Finding: The narrow range of 12 points (60 to 72) indicates a highly consistent level of performance among the students, with

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no outliers in the lower or upper extremes.

Grade Distribution Analysis: The following distribution is displayed to show the “Success Rate” of the research projects.

Table 4.7: Grade Distribution Analysis: A

Total Grade	Range
A	70-100%
B	60-69%
C/D/F	59-0%

Source: Authors’ estimation from the results of Research Project (ED 451) 2025, Department of English Language and Literature at Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri

Table 4.8: Grade Distribution Analysis: B

Grade	Total Scores Expected	Range of Scores Obtained
Proposal (PROP)	30%	15-30%
Supervision (SUP)	40%	34-40
Final Report (FIN)	30%	16-30%

Source: Authors’ estimation from the results of Research Project (ED 451) 2025, Department of English Language and Literature at Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Grade Distribution Analysis of Table A

The excellence rate (12.4%): The results indicate that a minority of students achieved the ‘A’ grade across the result sheets, reaching a total score of 70 and above.

The competency rate (100%): All the students successfully passed the course with at least a “B” (Credit) grade. This suggests that the supervisory framework within the department is highly effective at ensuring students meet the standardized quality threshold.

Component-Wise Performance

This was analysed with the Grade Distribution Analysis of Table B.

Proposal (PROP): Students consistently scored between 15 and 20 out of a total expected mark of 30%. This suggests a strong foundation in research methodology at the beginning of the research project. (See appendix for the full result sheet).

Final Report (FIN): Scores were stable between 15 and 20 out of the expected total marks of 30%. This implies that the technical writing and final submission standards were uniformly met.

Supervision (SUP): This was the primary “Grade Differentiator”. Scores ranged from 25 to 35 out of the total expected marks of 40%. Higher scores here directly correlated with the final “A” grade. This shows that active participation in supervision and external defence is the key factor for distinction. The results showed high internal consistency that students have a balanced mastery of the project phases (proposal, writing, and defence).

Academic Proficiency: The 100% pass rate at the “B” level reflects the academic rigor and quality of mentorship provided by the project supervisors. This suggests that TETFund- sponsored academic staff training and development improved the level of student research proficiency for the period in view.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study offers valuable insights on how TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development affects students’ academic performance and quality of teaching in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. The findings from research question one on the extent TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development contributed to the quality of teaching in AIFUE Owerri showed that the quality of teaching from TETFund-sponsored academic staff is above expectation with the pooled mean of 3.537 higher than the expected mean of 2.5. Findings from hypothesis one revealed that the correlation relationship between academic staff development and teaching quality is significant since the correlation probability value is 0.00, which is

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significant because it is less than 0.05. The results led to the rejection of null hypothesis one. The finding agrees with the view of Kani and Ezeodo (2023) who revealed that teachers who participated in workshops and seminars demonstrated better classroom management and improved instructional delivery especially in English and Mathematics. The study concluded that targeted professional development initiatives foster both teaching competence and student success.

Findings from research question two indicated that TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development influences students' academic performance. The results showed that the value of the pooled mean rating is 2.891 on a 4-point Likert scale which is higher than the expected mean of 2.5. Hypothesis two also revealed that the observed correlation coefficient of 0.000 is significant ($P < 0.05$) and therefore, led to the rejection of the stated null hypothesis. The TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development therefore, has a significant effect on student academic performance. To further provide a robust analysis, extracted data on Research Project course (ED 451) from the department of English Language and Literature between the period of March 2025 and June 2025 was assessed on the basis of the three weighted components of proposal (PROP), final (FIN), and supervision (SUP). The results collaborated on the efficacy of the findings from both the research question two and hypothesis two. The finding corroborates the observation of Hussaini, Uba, and Sifawa (2023) who revealed that staff development programs improve teacher performance in Nigeria. The finding also agrees with the view of Uzorka, Kalabuki, & Odebiyi (2024) who stated that teacher training programs and professional development enhance teaching quality and student performance.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the effect of TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development on quality of teaching and student academic performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. The study concluded that TETFund-sponsored academic staff training and development has a great effect on the quality of teaching, and subsequently, student academic performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. To ensure the sustainability of the gains of TETFund sponsorship, there is a need for a university policy on regular and continuous academic staff training and development that is all inclusive. This can only be achieved through structured annual staff training and development plans in partnership with TETFund and any other willing corporate sponsors to reduce financial constraints on academic staff.
2. Training and development should not only be associated with staff performance appraisal but also with improved teacher capacity for research, innovation and global competitiveness. This can be achieved through strategic training and development that translates into meaningful academic staff development outcomes which add value to both the educational institution and beyond.

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